

Fast Optical Look-up Operations on Integrated Photonic Memory Arrays

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Abstract: We experimentally present the first complete all-optical look-up memory operation at 10 Gb/s, utilizing two identical InP monolithically integrated PICs of multi-bit photonic-memory arrays, being able to operate as a 2-bit all-optical RAM or as 2-bit optical CAM tables.

1. Introduction

At the dawning of an Information-centric era, the widespread use of bandwidth-hungry cloud applications and the frantic scaling of line-rates have been driving the immense surge of data traffic, pushing for faster information processing and more efficient routing and switching technologies. Specifically, the increasing number of connected devices in current internet architectures, relying on virtual and logical networks overlying on-top of physical network topologies for enhanced network security, have led to a growing number of addressable end-points. This has resulted in increasing performance and latency bottlenecks, especially when a packet destination address needs to be looked-up within the optical line-rate and upon arrival of the packet. Although recent works of high port count optical switches with >25Tb/s capacity have favorably reduced latency values [1], processing of the header and forwarding is still carried out exclusively on slow performing electronic memories. In order to perform fast look-up and search memory operations, a variety of special hardware memories, called Content Addressable Memories (CAMs), are typically employed for implementing Address Look-Up (AL) tables [2]. CAMs support parallel comparison operations throughout the whole AL table in a single clock cycle. Although this allows for searching the whole CAM table and defining the egress port for next hop routing in one clock cycle, state of the art electronic CAMs are inherently bounded by their interconnect nature, typically performing around 400 MHz and hardly achieving speed up to 1 GHz [2].

To overcome the electronic memory bottlenecks and speed limitations of routing schemes, optics have started to penetrate the memory domain, proposing the development of ultra-fast alternative memory components. Various optical memory technologies, proposed during the last years, have resulted in the development of complete photonic CAM cell and Random-Access Memory (RAM) cell layouts [3][4] and proof of principle demonstrations of functional optical look-up and cache architectures with discrete components [5][6], highlighting the benefits of fast multi-bit photonic memory arrays. In this work, we present the development of the first 3-bit photonic memory array on a monolithically integrated InP platform. The structure includes two Semiconductor Optical Amplifier Mach-Zehnder (SOA-MZI) Cross-Phase modulation (XPM) and one bistable SOA-MZI Cross-Gain modulation (XGM), memory cells along with a SOA-MZI optical logic Access Gate (AG) and a 4x3 Arrayed Waveguide Grating (AWG), as a possible wavelength decoding control-unit, all in a single die. Such PICs have been fabricated and fully packaged, having demonstrated properties of complete reconfigurable photonic memory arrays [5][6], allowing for the development of an ultra-fast look-up operation directly in the optical domain.

2. Concept and Photonic Integrated Circuits of Photonic Memory Arrays

A conceptual schematic of the envisioned operation for a fast optical address look-up is depicted in Fig. 1(a), for an incoming optical packet that has a large packet payload (*green highlighted*) and a 2-bit destination address in its header

Fig.1. a) Conceptual schematic of a 2-bit address AL table, b) GDS mask layout of the photonic memory array, including three Flip-Flop memories, one multi-wavelength AG and a 4x3 AWG circuitry, c) microscope image of the PIC and d) photos of two packaged PIC memory prototypes.

Fig.2. a) Diagram of the selected CAM ‘00’ entry with the ‘01’ RAM entry and table of four possible CAM table entry lines, b) output spectrum of the 4x3 AWG and c-j) time-traces and eye diagram of the 2-bit optical CAM Matchline and RAM cell outputs.

(blue highlighted). The destination address forms the 2-bit word that needs to be searched in the AL table, upon arrival of the packet. The 2-bit incoming word is then broadcasted in parallel along the two columns of the depicted AL table, which hosts four entry-lines that store the ‘00’, ‘01’, ‘10’ and ‘11’ addresses and performs a fast parallel XNOR-based comparison that identifies if there is a “match” or not. In case there is a match, as e.g., in the fourth row, the CAM Matchline (ML) is activated, hence encoding a proper signal that can selectively activate the opposite row of the RAM table, that stores the egress port for next hop routing. In order to demonstrate this principle of operation, a monolithically integrated multi-bit photonic memory-array PIC, has been designed and fabricated on a monolithic InP platform. The PIC includes two bistable Flip-Flop memory bits based on SOA-MZI XPM units, one bistable waveguide memory based on a SOA-XGM unit, a SOA-MZI XNOR logic gate and a 4x3 AWG which holds the credentials for a wavelength encoding-decoding unit implementation. All the individual structures are marked and presented in the gds mask image of Fig. 1(b). A microscope photo of the PIC is shown in Fig. 1(c) and the two integrated chips, fabricated by HHI and opto-electronically packaged by PHIX, are shown in Fig. 1(d).

3. Experimental Results

The developed monolithic InP multi-bit photonic memory-array PICs have been partially employed in a 2-bit experimental AL operation, where they can potentially be configured either as complete 2-bit optical CAMs or 2-bit optical RAMs, similar to the testbed setup presented in [6]. The result of each of the four CAM ML comparison outputs is imprinted on a different wavelength based on the XNOR logic gate, acting as wavelength converter, followed ideally by a SOA-MZI AG and in this case the AWG that imprints and encodes each matching CAM ML output signal to a different RAM table entry. This operation can provide four indicative different possible connectivity links to an emulated 4x2-bit RAM table, as depicted in Fig. 2(a). The optical output spectrum of the InP AWG has been characterized and depicted in Fig. 2(b), which exhibits a Free Spectral Range (FSR) of 15.4 nm and a 3dB-channel bandwidth of 1.5 nm. The operation of the AL, at 10 Gb/s, is experimentally shown using the synchronized time traces shown in Fig. 2(c)-(i). The AL scheme presents the indicative case, where the CAM entry is ‘00’, for the stored CAM data. The Search line, CAM cell #1 and #2 and the Encoding/Decoding output signals reveal the logical principle of operation, prior enabling the RAM entry read signal, as shown in the time trace and eye diagram of Fig. 2(i) and (j). The Encoding/Decoding output features a logical ‘1’ only if the incoming search word and stored CAM data, both feature a logical ‘0’, as marked with the ‘green marker’, while in a different case the result will be a logical ‘0’. The final eye diagram of the RAM read out reveals an Extinction Ratio of 6 dB. The optical AL table was evaluated for four emulated look-up CAM-RAM entry lines, with the prospect of demonstrating eight possible combinations.

Conclusions

The development of two packaged monolithic InP CAM and RAM photonic memory arrays and the demonstration of an all-optical look-up operation are presented, paving the way towards a 10x speed up in look-up operations.

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